

VIII International Congress on Architectural Envelopes Breakthrough adaptable envelopes: a solution to accelerate the refurbishment of the existing building stock?

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Abstract

Today's measured rate of refurbishment is much lower than the one which should be observed to remain in line with Europe 2050 ambitions: there is a need to accelerate the market uptake and large-scale implementation of energy efficient refurbishment solutions thanks to innovative strategies. One of the most important components to be addressed with an innovative approach is the building envelope, which has to develop into an active rather than a passive element.

The EU funded BRESAER project is developing ground-breaking solutions for buildings refurbishment that can be adopted by the existing building stock throughout Europe. BRESAER envelope system includes combined active and passive pre-fabricated solutions integrated in a versatile lightweight structural mesh. The system is able to dynamically adapt to its environment thanks to an innovative Building Energy Management System. The aim of the project is to develop and demonstrate this envelope system, and prepare its future exploitation and commercialization.

This paper presents the first results and lessons learned on the challenges encountered while deploying the solution in a real environment and assessing its market potential. This includes constraints and potential barriers such as certification in different European countries, acceptance by the public and by the stakeholders of the construction sector, and financing high upfront investment costs. Routes to address these barriers (such as participation to standardization activities, implementation of innovative business models, and involvement of early adopters) will be explored.

1 Introduction

Only 1 to 2% of the building stock is replaced annually in the EC (less than 1% in some countries) [1]. Hence most of the energy savings required to meet the 2050 goals must come from existing buildings. More than half of the residential building stock was constructed before 1970 [2] and a majority of these buildings were constructed without consideration of energy efficiency criteria [3]. Although the targets to reach greater energy efficiency are residential buildings which represent about 75% of the total building stock and 63% of final energy consumption in the building sector, the retrofitting of non-residential buildings such as offices and educational buildings must also be addressed [4].

One of the most important components to be addressed with an innovative approach is the building envelope (roof, façade and basements), which has to be developed into an active rather than a passive element, meeting more functions than just the separation of the outer space from the interior with insulation. The façade represents the largest part of the heat transmission surface and includes a number of critical components (like windows, balconies, ventilation units, etc.), while facing thermal bridge phenomena. However, most solutions available in the market only offer thermal insulation, have poor aesthetics or are rather uniform in terms of applicability to different typologies of buildings and to different façade orientations. Climate and energy needs are also not properly considered. There is therefore a business opportunity in developing an energy efficient integrated and adaptable system that can be easily and quickly fitted to the façade of any residential building in Europe. Within this context, the Horizon 2020 project BRESAER (<http://www.bresaer.eu>) has been launched.

The BRESAER system is an innovative, cost-effective, adaptable and industrialized envelope system (façades and roofs) for buildings refurbishment including combined active and passive pre-fabricated solutions integrated in a versatile lightweight aluminium structural mesh. On the one hand, it is designed to accommodate further modifications (such as future renovation or technology upgrades). On the other hand, the envelope is able to adapt to a dynamic and intricate environment by measuring and processing multi-source information (e.g. outdoor and indoor environment conditions, occupancy, behaviour of users and envelope performance). The technological components integrated in BRESAER solution are:

- Dynamic window with automatic and controlled air-tightness and insulated solar blinds complementing energy saving and visual comfort strategies, such as light redirection and response to solar radiation
- Multifunctional and multilayer insulation panels made of Ultra High Performance Fibre Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC), to be used as rigid shells integrating an insulation material, with integrated PV film
- Combined solar thermal air and PV envelope component for indoor space heating and ventilation, thermal insulation and electricity generation
- Multifunctional lightweight ventilated façade module, with BIPV integrated on the cladding panel
- Combined thermal insulation and photocatalytic functional coating: Combining for the first time, the reflective properties of cool paints with the self-cleaning action of photocatalytic nanoparticles, a breakthrough coating will be applied on the exterior of the envelope components to improve its thermal properties and maintenance needs
- Cutting-edge Building Energy Management System able to measure and control both the envelope and hungry consuming devices using integrated simulation-based control techniques for automating the establishment of optimal operational plans
- Software tools to assist the design phase

Thanks to the industrialized process, easy assembly and maintenance, low intrusive installation and reduced timing of on-site works, and because of the high potential of energy demand reduction, the BRESAER solution is expected to be cost-effective comparing with other traditional refurbishment techniques. The objective fixed by the project is to meet a payback period lower than 7 years. The BRESAER system is to be implemented in a physical demonstration site and assessed in three case studies. The selected buildings to do so will cover different European climate zones and assorted building types, constructed before the EPBD requirements were enacted, with a standard envelope to guarantee its high replication and exploitation potential.

2 Barriers towards BRESAER solution(s) implementation

Beyond the technical specifications and challenges of the project, this section will focus on the barriers encountered in different aspects of BRESAER deployment such as regulative, societal and financial hurdles. These non-technical barriers play a key role in the progress and success of an innovative project as commented in the next subsections.

2.1 National regulations and certification

A number of technical and social criteria have been considered when selecting the location of the BRESAER physical demonstration. From a technical perspective, the impact of BRESEAR on energy savings should be relevant for all EU climatic conditions. Therefore, the demo building must represent various climatic conditions, which generate both heating and cooling demands. The city of Ankara, Turkey, was chosen when planning the project to host the physical demo of BRESAER. Ankara has a very special climate with temperatures ranging from -15 to 35°C and large shifts between day and night which can provide efficient applications of thermal storage technologies. The BRESAER solution were to be demonstrated in Kecioren, a largely populated district municipality in Ankara, Turkey. The building involved is used by the Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Turkey (MoNE) as a life-long educational centre for adults.

When the BRESAER solution was conceived, its technical solutions were designed to comply with the European regulations at every level. In particular, the solutions would comply with the European reaction to fire specifications in several countries [5] which would correspond to a ‘B level’ for this type of building envelopes. At that moment, Turkey was in line with this EU fire specifications, in particular when dealing with educational buildings. However, the Turkish regulation, issued by the Ministry of Urbanization of Turkey, changed during 2015 when the project was already on track and BRESAER demo to be deployed in Turkey, requiring a very high classification for the envelope system reaction to fire (A2)¹. In order to technically corroborate this potential barrier, EMI (the Hungarian institution for Quality Control and Innovation in Building) has carried out a series of tests to certify the behaviour of the system against fire, wind and impact, among others. The results have shown that BRESAER complies with the European regulation as foreseen, but not with Turkish regulation for educational buildings anymore, which in this case is more restrictive.

Certification and standardisation are other key aspects to take into account when developing, manufacturing and deploying an innovative solution such as BRESAER. To be authorised to enter a

¹ For the buildings in Turkey, the required reaction to fire classes are divided in two according to the façade types, as follows: 1) For facades with mechanical substructure and air gap, at least “hard to ignite” (corresponds to Class A2 of EN 13501 according to Turkish definitions) is required for every component of the façade system. 2) For conventional façade systems (like concrete and plaster, or glued façades), at least “hard to burn” (corresponds to Class C of EN 13501 according to Turkish definitions) is required.

market and for insurability purposes, the system must indeed be certified in every country where it is to be installed, as certification procedures change from one country to another. BRESAER system as a whole could apply for an EC marking², in order to be able to sell the solution throughout the EU without having to carry out further tests. A prerequisite is that the system needs to be defined by a European standard or use a European Assessment Document (EAD) or European Technical Approval Guideline (ETAG) or a Common Understanding Approval Procedure (CUAP), to define all the tests to be done. However, no European standard exists today for the certification of a façade system such as BRESAER. The European Technical Approval Guideline ETAG 034 “Guideline for European Technical Approval of Kits for External Wall Claddings” is the most relevant ETAG, but covers BRESAER only partially. The BRESAER consortium has therefore made a pre-normative research in the project in order to complete or reinforce existing European standards. BRESAER is interacting with technical committees identified as relevant, in particular those related to the BRESAER system and components, but also energy related ones (i.e. CEN/TC 371 "Project Committee - Energy Performance of Building project group", ISO/TC 205/WG 2 "Design of energy-efficient buildings"...). The standardisation activities of BRESAER are foreseen to be a facilitator of the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the BRESAER solutions, in line with its exploitation strategy.

2.2 Stakeholders acceptance issues

It has been proved that social awareness and willingness are very important factors that could foster or limit the massive deployment of energy efficient solutions such as buildings’ retrofitting [6]. Meaning that energy efficiency, CO₂ reduction and practically all the goals to be reached to contribute to the world’s energy transition not only depend on technological progress and expertise but also on societal behaviour (social strata). Therefore, technological developments should take into account the new knowledge brought by social sciences to gain a better understanding of end-users’ expectations and increase their engagement and acceptance.

For instance, parameters such as aesthetic preferences can have a very large impact on social acceptance when deploying innovative solutions. As commented by Darnton and Evans 2013 [7] these kind of preferences are social phenomena that could relate people to particular social groups and behaviour. As a consequence, inhabitants/occupants of the property will worry about the appearance of the building after retrofitting [8]. There are also positive response towards buildings’ renovation as shown by the research study performed by Scott et al. [9] in which inhabitants of North of England, were asked the 'best thing' about energy efficiency improvements proposed for their neighbourhood: one of the most popular answers was that these retrofitting solutions would improve the appearance of the home and the neighbourhood. The situation of being the ‘good example’ for the community and the proudness of the inhabitants were also important drivers to achieve the improvements.

BRESAER aimed at retrofitting one building located near Madrid (Spain), offering all the conditions to be in line with Spanish regulations, and technical and climatic requirements for a successful deployment of the integrated solution. However, aesthetical functions hindered the final adoption of the technology by the owner of the building.

² By affixing the CE marking to a product, a manufacturer declares that the product meets all the legal requirements (meet high safety, health, and environmental protection requirements) for CE marking and can be sold throughout the European Economic Area (EEA).

2.3 Financial barriers, Payback time

The payback period is defined as the time it takes to recover investment costs, in terms of profit of savings. This financial parameter is frequently used to assess an investment and determine the attractiveness of a project. The objective of BRESAER is to meet a payback time of less than 7 years, which is the target provided by the European Commission to ensure fast market uptake.

To calculate the payback time of BRESAER, 2 scenarios in 3 different case studies were used. The payback period calculation was performed based on the actual investments required to retrofit the building and the differential energy performance achieved by the system. The differential energy performance resulted in a reduction of the running costs of the building. The case studies analysed are an educational building in Ankara, Turkey³, a residential building in Prague, Czech Republic and an office building in Athens, Greece. The description of the scenarios used for the calculations is:

- The “least energy cost scenario” taking into account the least energy consumption option from the energy analysis of the project, which uses combined solar thermal air and PV envelope solution, one of the system panels for opaque areas of the building, the dynamic windows and the automatic controlled insulated blinds.
- The “least investment cost scenario” characterized by the combination of only the solution for opaque areas, the dynamic windows and the automatic controlled insulated blinds.

The results of these calculations are shown in the following table:

Table 1: Payback time of the BRESAER solution in different scenarios and countries (virtual demos)⁴

Scenarios	Payback period (years)		
	Athens	Ankara	Prague
Least energy cost	>30	>30	>30
Least investment cost	20-21	>30	17-18

The payback period for both scenarios in the simulated buildings is much higher than the 7-year target. These results are in line with other similar studies, and regular practice in the sector, where the decision to retrofit buildings is commonly taken due to non-energy-related functional needs. In this way, energy performance improvement is an added value to a retrofit that would be performed anyway. Still, strategies have been searched for reducing this payback time beyond the optimisation of the BRESAER solutions costs so as to make it look ‘more attractive’ for all the stakeholders.

2.4 Financial strategies, ‘Green parameters’

The so called ‘green parameters’ could help to reduce the payback time of the BRESAER solution. The notion of green value is defined as the net additional value of a property created through a better environmental performance (this environmental performance can be related to various parameters: the energy performance, the accessibility to public transport, the use of renewable energy, the construction materials used, the attribution of an environmental performance label, etc.) [10]. We will here focus on the green value related to energy. For instance, economic elements that may constitute the green value include monthly fees reduction (energy bill, water consumption, maintenance costs...), increase in

³ BRESAER had already some data gathered when analysing this building for a potential deployment of the project making of this case study, interesting to be assessed further and achievable for theoretical purposes.

⁴ The costs used to calculate the payback period of the BRESAER solutions were industrialised approximations and not prototype costs.

occupancy rate, rent and sale prices per m², capitalisation rate, etc. On the other hand, the green value also includes elements that are difficult to quantify such as indoor comfort (thermal comfort), accessibility, health (air quality, thermal comfort, humidity...), social value (to address fuel poverty), attractiveness for the buyers and renters (positive image of a “green” property), benefits of the lower environmental impact, etc. Different studies and references show the use of these parameters [11,12,13] but do not exactly explain how to capitalise them. However, in order to ensure that the methodology followed remains ‘credible’ for financial officers of landlords when taking the decision to adopt BRESAER, the calculation methods were updated only to incorporate value streams which have been corroborated numerically in official registers.

The case study presented in this section is related to the residential building in Prague under the “least investment cost scenario” conditions. The outcomes presented in the table below are to highlight the difference of the payback period when using ‘green parameters’, for instance increasing the building’s value (i.e. 0 and 4-7%) by using the BRESAER solution.

Table 2: Payback period for the BRESER solution in a residential building in Prague under the “least investment cost scenario” increasing the value of the building from 4 to 7% (Green Value parameter).

Least investment scenario	Residential building (Prague, Czech Republic)				
Increased building value	0%	4%	5%	6%	7%
Payback period	17 to 18 years	9 to 10 years	7 to 8 years	6 to 7 years	4 to 5 years

These new results reflect the full value delivered by the BRESAER system and provide more information to investors, owners and inhabitants in order to provide them a broader perspective of the economic benefits that a retrofit solution like BRESAR may bring to them. More case studies using ‘green parameters’ are being developed within the project, for instance taking into account the savings reached thanks to building’s retrofitting avoiding classical maintenance during the building’s lifetime. In ‘standard’ conditions, not taking into account ‘green parameters’, the BRESAER solution would need a cost not above 70€/m² to achieve a 7 year of payback. The order of magnitude of this price corresponds to a ‘conventional’ ETICS (External Thermal Insulation Composite System) in Spain for example. A solution like BRESAER will certainly bring more advantages not only regarding energy efficiency but also by increasing the value of the building and benefits for its inhabitants.

3 Discussion and recommendations

Innovative adaptable envelopes such as the BRESAER system must overcome different barriers to penetrate the market of building refurbishment. Most of these barriers are also faced by ‘off-the-shelf’ retrofitting technologies such as ETICS, and some – presented in the previous section – are specific to innovative solutions. In addition, the project is working on implementing or developing best practices to address the challenges of certification, user acceptance and cost.

3.1 Certification and standardisation

Certification and standardisation practices should be surveyed at a very early stage of the project to prevent delays related to comply with regulation and standards, and facilitate the future exploitation of the technologies developed, their acceptance and utilisation by the market. It is therefore advised to interact with EU Standardisation Technical Committees so as to participate in standardisation definitions and exchange with the market stakeholders. A project should also constantly monitor the evolution of building codes and building regulations to avoid non-compliances.

3.2 Market and social acceptance

Social as well as market aspects should not be neglected by innovative projects. Stakeholders and end-users needs and expectations should be thoroughly assessed to ensure that the developed technology meets these needs and facilitate the technological deployment. This assessment can be implemented thanks to the identification of potential early-adopters and the study of their expectations through interviews. This interaction with early-adopters enables innovative projects to test their value proposition with future clients and users and validate that what is proposed matches the demand. Fine-tuning of value proposition to better address the needs and maximise acceptance is then possible.

3.3 Mitigating the high upfront investment cost

High investment costs and low payback time are very important barriers, which may further hinder social acceptance and differ the market uptake of an innovative solution. It should first be highlighted that payback period has serious limitations because it does not account for the time value of money, risk or the fact that returns to the investment continue after the payback period. Alternative measures of "return" preferred by economists are Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR). The IRR allows to see the actual yields, expressed as an interest rate, the investment creates [14].

Payback method is often applied for assessing profitability of measures in the building sector as it is easy to apply and easy to understand. However it encourages investments profitable in the short-term, and not investments delivering the highest energy savings. Also, it is not a profitability model and it does not take into account interest rates, changes in energy prices, the economic lifetime of the measure or possible needs for re-investments. If the investments to be assessed have long economic lifetimes and are expected to be in operation for a long time they will not be treated fairly using this method, as explained by the Total Concept method [14]. For instance, the IRR has been used as financial parameter within the CITYFiED project where the length of energy performance contracts for energy retrofitting were about 15-20 years [15]. This demonstrates that it is feasible to implement retrofitting solutions with long payback time, even with significant investments, as they bring higher benefits during long periods of time. Different financial parameters (IRR, NPV) should therefore be used in addition to payback time when assessing a project, in order to have a more complete evaluation, also accounting on the nature of the project and its level of innovation.

4 Conclusions

The refurbishment of the existing building stock requires ground-breaking strategies in order to meet targets for reduced energy use and greenhouse gas emissions. The BRESAER system aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative envelop system that uses cost-effective, adaptable solutions for building refurbishment. The project will achieve primary energy savings, increase of comfort, contribution in reduction of CO₂ emissions and costs and financial attractiveness towards exploitation in different climatic zones all over Europe due its high replicability and easy installation.

BRESAER will continue working very close with the EU standardisation Technical Committees to facilitate the exploitation, replicability, adaptability and market uptake. In addition, the project surveys carefully regulation evolution in the countries where BRESAER can be deployed. The project will intensify the actions addressing the barriers presented in this article. This includes performing detailed financial analyses and looking for innovative business models to mitigate the high upfront investment cost, and adjusting the value proposition (e.g. customisation, easy installation) to increase users' acceptance and the attractiveness of BRESAER system. Because of the high degree of industrialization

of the BRESAER system, it indeed offers opportunities to reduce the construction process times and occupational hazard, incrementing installation security. It is conceived as a low-intrusive solution for inhabitants. To sum up, BRESAER solution can contribute to renovate the enormous building stock (with no cultural value) needed of intervention in Europe.

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